

REVIEWING IMPACT OF ALCOHOL AND DRUG ABUSE IN HEALTH OF ADOLESCENT

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Drug abuse is the improper use of or application of drug by a person without proper knowledge of the drug and without due prescription from a qualified medical practitioner. However, drug misuse is defined as the use of a substance for a purpose not consistent with legal or medical guideline. Drugs that can be abused include: Amphetamines, Anabolic steroids, alcohol, Marijuana (Cannabis or Indian hemp), cocaine, heroin, caffeine, barbiturates, narcotic, inhalants, codeine and cough syrup. Drug abuse and misuse is now rampant among adolescents. It has a negative impact on physical health, social and emotional health. It can even affect the functions of the brain and other vital organs in the body. The issue of drug abuse among adolescents can be resolved through health education, drug testing, showing of good examples by parents and teachers. Why adolescent abuse drugs particularly, peer pressure, social environment, broken home, ignorance, and availability of hard drugs. Effects of drug abuse on adolescents who abuse drugs are at particular risk for negative consequences. Emotional problems, behavioral problems, addiction and dependence, risky sex, learning problems, diseases, and brain damage. Some solutions for drug abuse and misuse. Health education, counselling, drug testing.

KEYWORDS: Drug abuse, misuse, Health of adolescent, impact of drug on adolescent

INTRODUCTION

A drug is any chemical substance that causes a change in an organism's physiology or psychology when consumed (Stedman's Medical Dictionary, 2014). In pharmacology, a drug is a chemical substance, typically of known structure, which, when administered to a living organism, produces a biological effect. A pharmaceutical drug, also called a medication or medicine, is a chemical substance used to treat, cure, prevent, or diagnose a disease or to promote well-being (Rang, Dale, Ritter and Henderson 2011, p.1). Drug is a very strong substance, made from different grains and herbs with the mixture of many strong chemicals which has very serious short-term and long-term effects (Rang *et al.*, 2011). The word drug means any substances or chemicals prescribed for medical reasons. However, it is one of the substances which alter the way the body functions.

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Drug abuse is the use of a mood or behaviour altering substance resulting in significant impairment or distress. (Abdullahi, 2019, p. 19) viewed drug abuse as the use of drugs to the extent that it interferes with the health and social function of an individual. (Agwubike, 2018) opined that drug abuse is the improper use or application of drugs by a person without proper knowledge of the drugs and without due prescription from a qualified medical practitioner. This definition focuses on psychoactive drugs; all drugs can be abused to the extent that it turns into addiction when the drug user is unable to stop the use of drugs despite the harmful effects on users' physical and emotional feelings. According to (Agwubike, 2018) examples of drugs commonly abused by adolescents are; Amphetamines, Anabolic steroids, alcohol, Marijuana (Cannabis or Indian hemp), cocaine, heroin, caffeine, barbiturates, amphetamines, methamphetamine (also called mkpuru mmiri in Igbo Language), narcotic, inhalants, codeine and cough syrup; which have excitatory or inhibitory effect which are thought to enhance performance in sport by delaying the onset of fatigue, hasten recovery rate or provide long lasting energy for work

On the other hand, Drug misuse is defined as the use of a substance for a purpose not consistent with legal or medical guidelines (WHO, 2016). It has a negative impact on health or functioning and may take the form of drug dependence, or be part of a wider spectrum of problematic or harmful behaviour. In the UK, the Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs (ACMD) characterises problem drug use as a condition that may cause an individual to experience social, psychological, physical or legal problems related to intoxication and/or regular excessive consumption, and/or dependence (ACMD, 2018).

Sawyer, Azzopardi , Wickremarathne , Patton, (2018) stated that the adolescent stage starts at age 10 and should end at 24, inferring to the developmental consequences of the age group on laws, social policies and service systems as the reason for the extended range. Meanwhile, the American Academy of Paediatrics (AAP) specified an age bracket starting from 11 years to 21 years as the age range of adolescence (AAP, 2021). According to Odejide *et al.*, (2017) Adolescents abuse most of the psychoactive drugs such as alcohol and cigarettes which creates problems for them and the society. These drugs are mostly abused because they are readily available (Okoza *et al.*, 2009). Studies showed that parenting has a lot of influence on early initiation into use of drugs by adolescents. Hawkins *et al.*, (2017) argued that children who received good supervision and consistent discipline from their parents in their early years in life are less likely to engage in drug abuse. The use of alcohol, tobacco, cannabis and other psychoactive substances constitutes one of most important public health problems among adolescents worldwide (Oshodi *et al.*, 2010).

Drug abuse and misuse seriously affect the individuals health and social function, it also hurt the users family, friends and colleagues and society as a whole. Drug abuse and misuse has broken up more homes, murdered more human beings, started more war, wrecked more careers, e.t.c Ejikeme (2013), equally identify problems associated with drug and alcohol abuse to include insomnia, injuries or even death incurred while driving etc under the influence of drug abuse increasing, likelihood of involvement in animal behaviour (to finance the addiction); sickness resulting from the neglect of personal hygiene, toxic psychoses (may be precipitate by a single dose). Memory difficulties, high blood pressure, manpower loss, violent behaviour and socially undesirable behaviour.

CONCEPT OF DRUG ABUSE AND MISUSE

Drug Abuse

Drug abuse is said to be the use of a mood or behaviour altering substance resulting in significant impairment or distress. Abdullahi (2019) viewed drug abuse as the use of drugs to the extent that it distorts the health and social function of an individual. Agwubike (2018) opined that drug abuse is the improper use or application of drugs by a person without proper knowledge of the drugs and without due prescription from a qualified medical practitioner. This definition focuses on psychoactive drugs; all drugs can be abused to the extent that it turns into addiction when the drug user is unable to stop the use of drugs despite the harmful effects on users' physical and emotional feelings. According to Agwubike (2018) drugs commonly abused by adolescents are; Amphetamines, Anabolic steroids, alcohol, Marijuana (Cannabis or Indian hemp), cocaine, heroin, caffeine, barbiturates, amphetamines, narcotic, inhalants, codeine and cough syrup; which have excitatory or inhibitory effect which are thought to enhance performance in sport by delaying the onset of fatigue, hasten recovery rate or provide long lasting energy for work. Boris (2014) say drug abuse can play or serve a significant role in everyday interpersonal affairs and many adolescent in Nigeria are use.

Drug Misuse

Drug misuse is defined as the use of a substance for a purpose not consistent with legal or medical guidelines (WHO, 2016). It has a negative impact on health or functioning and may take the form of drug dependence, or be part of a wider spectrum of problematic or harmful behaviour (DH, 2016). In the UK, the Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs (ACMD) characterises problem drug use as a condition that may cause an individual to experience social, psychological, physical or legal problems related to intoxication and/or regular excessive consumption, and/or dependence (ACMD, 2018).

Repeated use of a drug can lead to the development of tolerance in which increased doses of the drug are required to produce the same effect. Tolerance develops to opioids, stimulants and cannabis. Cessation of use leads to reduced tolerance and this may present significant risks for individuals who return to drug doses at a level to which they had previously developed tolerance. This can result in accidental overdoses and, in the case of opioid misuse, could lead to respiratory depression and death. Withdrawal syndromes have clearly been identified after cessation or reduction of opioid and stimulant use. DSM-IV criteria for a withdrawal disorder include the development of a substance-specific syndrome due to cessation or reduction in use; the syndrome causing clinically significant distress; and symptoms not due to a general medical condition or better explained by another mental disorder (APA,2014). Opioids, stimulants and cannabis also produce intoxication, that is, disturbances in psycho-physiological functions and responses, including consciousness, cognition and behaviour, following administration (WHO, 2016). Adolescents who misuse drugs may encounter many of health and social problems other than dependence, which may include (particularly with opioid users): physical health problems (for example, thrombosis, abscesses, overdose, hepatitis B and C, HIV, and respiratory and cardiac problems) mental health problems (for example, depression, anxiety, paranoia and suicidal thoughts) social difficulties (for example, relationship problems, financial difficulties, unemployment and homelessness) criminal justice problems.

Alcohol misuse is also common in all types of people who misuse drugs; data from the National Treatment Outcomes Research Study (NTORS) on drug misuse suggested that 22% of participants also drank alcohol frequently, 17% drank extremely heavily and 8% drank an

excessive amount on a daily basis (Karthryn, Sara and Shelly 2014). People who misuse opioids in particular may often take a cocktail of substances, including alcohol, cannabis and prescribed drugs such as benzodiazepines, which can have especially dangerous effects in comparison with one of the drugs taken individually. Drug dependence is associated with a high incidence of criminal activity, with associated costs to the criminal justice system in the UK estimated as reaching £1 billion per annum in 1996 (United Kingdom Anti-Drugs Coordinating Unit, more than 17,000 offences were reported by an NTORS cohort of 753 participants in a 90-day period before entering treatment (Karthryn et al 2014)

SOME OF THE DRUGS THAT CAN BE ABUSED AND MISUSED AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS TO HEALTH

Narcotics

Narcotics are addictive drugs that reduce the user's perception of pain and induce euphoria (a feeling of exaggerated and unrealistic well-being). These are drugs which include opium and its derivatives, morphine, heroin and codeine which provide relief to pain, anxiety and tension. Medically they are used to relief Pain, treat diarrhoea and stop coughing (Ugwuoke, Mfon and Omotala. 2019).

Barbiturates

Barbiturates are synthetic drugs used in medicine to depress the central nervous system. The effects range from mild sedation to coma and they may be used as sedatives, hypnotics or as part of anaesthesia. Some barbiturates are used to relieve tension or anxiety prior to surgery. It is also depressants like alcohol. They produced light headedness, ease tension, and induce relaxation and sleep. Large doses can slow vital body functions and can cause death (Anumonye, 2018).

Alcohol

Alcohol abuse causes neuro-inflammation and leads to myelin disruptions and white matter loss; the developing adolescent brain is at increased risk of brain damage and other long lasting alterations to the brain (Lakshmi,Asokan and Samad, 2017). Adolescents with an alcohol use disorder damage the hippocampal, prefrontal cortex, and temporal lobes (Lakshmi *et al.*, 2010). Adolescents who consume alcohol heavily display symptoms of conduct disorder. Its symptoms include troublesome behavior in school, constantly lying, learning disabilities and social impairments (Mc Ardle, Paul, 2017). Alcohol slows brain activity and muscle reaction and continued use of it can result in indigestion, ulcers, degeneration of the brain and cirrhosis of the liver.

Amphetamines

Amphetamines are a group of synthetic psychoactive drugs called central nervous system (CNS) stimulants. It is a central nervous system stimulants that affect chemicals in the brain and nerves that contribute to hyperactivity and impulse control. They cause brain damage while combining them with barbiturates; is extremely dangerous (Anumonye, 2010).

Inhalants

The inhalation of certain chemicals found in glue, gasoline, paint thinner, fingernail polish remover, household cement, petroleum and the like produces a high, sometimes accompanied by dizziness, loss of judgement and aggressiveness (Anumonye, 2010).

Marijuana

(Cannabis or Indian hemp) Marijuana is locally called "Ganye" "wee-wee" to mention just a few. Marijuana is the most commonly used drug after tobacco and alcohol, particularly among youths (Ugwuoke *et al*, 2019).

Codeine

Codeine has become a major drug abused by youths in Nigeria. Its common effects include drowsiness and constipation. Less common are euphoria, itching, nausea, vomiting, dry mouth, orthostatic hypotension, urinary retention, depression, and paradoxical coughing. It also effects include suppresses the Central Nervous System (CNS), constricts the vessels, causing constipation, nausea etc., (Ugwuoke *et al*, 2019).

REASONS WHY ADOLESCENTS ABUSE DRUGS

Recent studies in African countries have shown that the phenomenon of drug use is also common in this continent and is becoming one of the most disturbing health-related problems among adolescents (Igwe *et al.*, 2019). Studies shows that there is an increasing incidence in the use, and a decreasing age of onset, of these substances (Fatoye and Morakinyo, 2012)

Most adolescents begin their use of drugs with alcohol and cigarettes and later progress to more dangerous substances such as cannabis and cocaine (Fatoye *et al.*, 2016). Several psychosocial factors have been associated with drug abuse. Particularly, Peer Pressure, Social environment, Broken home, Ignorance, Availability of hard drug, Media portrayal of drug - use by celebrities, insecurity, personal conflict, anxiety (Elliott, 2018).

GENERAL EFFECTS OF DRUG ABUSE ON ADOLESCENTS

Drug abuse at any age can cause serious health effects, but adolescents who abuse drugs are at particular risk for negative consequences. Adolescents who abuse drugs are more likely to struggle with addiction later in life and have permanent and irreversible brain damage. Some other common negative

effects of drug abuse on adolescents are:

1) **Emotional problems;** Drug abuse can cause or mask emotional problems such as anxiety, depression, mood swings, suicidal thoughts and schizophrenia. Drug use can also increase the severity of these emotional problems. For example, adolescents that use marijuana weekly double their risk of depression and anxiety (APA, 2019)

2) **Behavioral problems;** Teens who abuse drugs have an increased risk of social problems, depression, suicidal thoughts and violence. According to a recent survey by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, teens who abuse drugs are more likely than teens who don't abuse drugs to engage in delinquent behaviors such as fighting and stealing.

3) **Addiction and dependence;** In this content, dependence is defined as a strong desire or sense of compulsion to take a substance, a difficulty in controlling its use, the presence of a physiological withdrawal state, tolerance of the use of the drug, neglect of alternative pleasures and interests and persistent use of the drug, despite harm to oneself and others (WHO, 2016). Dependence is diagnosed according to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM- IV) when three or more of the following criteria are present in a

12-month period: tolerance; withdrawal; increasing use over time; persistent or unsuccessful attempts to reduce use; preoccupation or excessive time spent on use or recovery from use; negative impact on social, occupational or recreational activity; and continued use despite evidence of its causing psychological or physical problems (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2019). The diagnosis of dependence is clearest with opioids.

The WHO states that: ‘opioid dependence develops after a period of regular use of opioids, with the time required varying according to the quantity, frequency and route of administration, as well as factors of individual vulnerability and the context in which drug use occurs. Opioid dependence is not just a heavy use of the drug but a complex health connotation that has social, psychological and biological determinants and consequences, including changes in the brain. It is not a weakness of character or will.’ (WHO, 2016) However, dependence, as characterised by the above definition, can also occur with stimulants and cannabis. Studies prove that the younger/a person is when they begin using drugs the more likely they/are to develop a substance abuse problem and relapse later in life.

4) **Risky sex;** Teens that use drugs are five times more likely to have sex than teens who don’t use drugs. Teens that use drugs are also more likely to have unprotected sex and have sex with a stranger. This leads to higher risks of STDs, teen pregnancy and sexual assault (Karthryn *et al* 2014).

5) **Learning problems;** Drug abuse damages short-term and/long-term memory and can lead to problems with learning and memory later in life.

6) **Diseases;** Teens who abuse drugs with needles increase their risk of blood-borne diseases like HIV, AIDS and Hepatitis B and C.

7) **Brain damage;** Drug abuse among teens can result in serious mental disorders or permanent, irreversible damage to the brain or nervous system. Brain damage among teens who abuse drugs includes brain shrinkage; impaired learning abilities; amnesia and memory problems; impaired reasoning, perception and intuition; increased or decreased socialization; and changes in sexual desire (Lakshmi *et al.*, 2010).

SOLUTIONS TO DRUG ABUSE AND MISUSE AMONG ADOLESCENTS

According to National Institute of Health (NIH, 2016), the problem of drug abuse can be solved through the following ways:

Heath Education; this should help in educating the adolescents and the masses about the dangers associated with drug abuse and excessive alcohol consumption.

Counselling; Adolescents need adequate in all aspect of livelihood especially in the aspect of drugs and alcohol uses.

Parents should start from home to give their children proper training and good examples.

Drug testing can also be a means of helping youth and adolescents overcome denial of their substance abuse.

Teachers in their parts should be models for the adolescents and the society at large.

Conclusion: Since drug abuse and delinquency (which is common in adoliscents.)are inextricable interrelated ,identifying substance-abusing adoliscent at home and school are important step for intervening in both their substance abuse and other delinquent behaviour

they exhibit. Drug identification strategies, followed by effective interventions, help prevent further abuse of drug and misuse and among adolescents. Drug testing can be a constructive means of helping youth and adolescents overcome denial of their substance abuse. As a part of intervention drug testing can be used to help youth achieve and maintain recovery and curtail other deviant behaviours. Over time, effective drug identification will help the society and other health agencies achieve the goal of balance approach including community protection, youth accountability, and competency development.

Recommendations: There should be interventions which include a wide spectrum of actions intended to prevent, delay, or reduce drug abuse and misuse among adolescents. Parents and teachers should report any child that is involved in the illegal drug use to the appropriate authorities. All adolescents should be screened for alcohol and illegal drug use. Based on the results, clinicians should conduct further assessment, provide guidance and brief counselling interventions, and if appropriate, refer for treatment. For adolescents reporting no substance use, there should be a positive reinforcement. There should be screening and health education for risky behaviours, including substance use. Clinicians should also explore the option of providing preventive drug misuse activities and assess persons at risk of illicit drug misuse. Clinicians should also consider providing skills training to young persons who are assessed as vulnerable to illicit and non-medical drug use. That government should enact a law that will forbid politicians from using youth as a political thing.

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